

AERODYNAMIC AND AEROTHERMODYNAMIC INVESTIGATION FOR AEROSHAPE AND FLYING QUALITIES OF THE ICARUS RE-ENTRY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

ICARUS is a project funded by the European Union's HORIZON EUROPE (HE) program under the grant agreement No 101134997.

It targets to bring up to TRL6 the maturation of enabling technologies in the field of re-usable space transportation systems, addressing the innovative re-entry solution based on Inflatable Heat Shields (IHS), deemed applicable for recovery of Launch Vehicles stages.

This paper presents the system design of the Aerodemonstrator solution with a particular focus on aeroshape investigation and definition, aerodynamic and aerothermodynamic characterization, flying qualities and static stability assessment. 2D-axisymmetric and 3D CFD simulations have been performed with the ONERA code CEDRE/CHARME on the various aeroshape designs under study, for various flight conditions extracted along referenced flight trajectories and IHS attitude. Low supersonic to hypersonic flows, from Mach 1.41 up to Mach 6.5 (entry velocity), have been yet simulated, assuming turbulent boundary layer. The Aerodynamic Database (AEDB) composed of aerodynamic force and moment coefficients and associated uncertainties from EFESTO-2 HE project legacy, as well as the location of the pressure center have been used to assess the flying qualities analysis.

The convective-diffusive heat flux calculated assuming both radiative equilibrium at the wall and/or cold isothermal wall condition are used to size the flexible Thermal Protection System, and guide the choice and positions of sensors (Health Monitoring System Work Package). The obtained results and consecutive analysis, which led our design choices, are discussed in perspective of the IHS aero-demonstrator.

Index Terms— Inflatable Heat Shields, Re-entry Technologies, Aerodynamic and Aerothermodynamic investigation, Flying Quality, Launchers Reusability, Flexible TPS

1. INTRODUCTION

ICARUS stands for “Inflatable Concept Aero-shell for the Recovery of a re-Usable launcher Stage” project is a flight

demonstration initiative aiming at bringing together the results obtained so-far in EFESTO and EFESTO-2 projects - funded by the European Commission respectively under the programs H2020 (2019-2022) and under Horizon Europe (2022-2024) - with in addition a significant delta-development together with validation of the technologies and system capabilities in a flight-relevant environment.

In order to demonstrate applicability of this innovative solution for the purpose above mentioned, the project will pursue the following end goals [1]:

- a) Complete the maturation on ground of the key technologies as Flexible TPS, Inflatable Structure and Health Monitoring Sensors;
- b) Carry out a mission/system design loop to realize and fly (in relevant environment) a meaningful-scale demonstrator of an Inflatable Heat Shield through a flight on board a sounding rocket;
- c) Execute post-flight analysis and numerical rebuilding for technology performance evaluation, system behavior identification, and models verification/cross-correlation.

In the early aeroshape definition phase, an evaluation of the influence of various parameters (IHS shape, tube length payload, flight conditions, wall heat flux assessment) on the aerodynamic force and moment coefficients as well as on wall heating distribution is performed to determine the optimal trajectory and the flying quality of the HIS but also to address key parameters of the flexible TPS.

After fixing the geometric shape and numerical parameters of Navier-Stokes simulations, an important CFD database has been built to consolidate the mission, system, sub-systems and TPS design objectives. The aeroshape and mission definitions are developed inside a loop including all the investigation fields.

2. EARLY AEROSHAPE DESIGN

To initiate the design loop, a suitable IHS geometry within an inflated state has to be defined. This step allowed to obtain the potential geometry shape and size in terms of cone angle, diameter, nose radius, and ballistic coefficient.

The exploration relied on investigating the feasible local entry corridor (LEC) in compliance with fundamental

constraints to be respected, namely maximum aerothermal loads (heat flux and heat time-integral) and maximum mechanical loads (dynamic pressure and g-levels). For this to be done, adoption of reasonable figures of some key parameters was based on consortium heritage in re-entry mission, with a specific link to EFESTO and EFESTO-2 heritage. Reasonable ranges of values were established for the mass and drag of the re-entry system, and a range of trajectories was propagated based on the initial conditions assured by the launch vehicle as velocity, altitude and attitude at separation. The main output of the LEC analyses was a range of potential ballistic coefficients that ensure the mission to occur in fully compliance with the corridor given by the constraints. Afterwards, a reference ballistic coefficient (BC) is then retained that can ensure a required margin. From this reference BC, reference mass, surface and drag of the re-entry system were assessed. In that regard, the reference geometry chosen for ICARUS exhibits a diameter of 3.0 m and a cone angle of 120°. The nose-radius is obtained by geometric rules. Such choice is then justified by some main factors:

- The classical sphere-cone combination of nose and body is the most appropriate one as widely analysed during EFESTO-1 and EFESTO-2 project [2];
- 120deg shape factor is preferred because in continuity with EFESTO-1 and EFESTO-2 heritage, to maximise the full set of lessons learned vis-à-vis shape design and ATD investigation, as well as inflated heat shield design;
- 3 m diameter is a reasonable value for an intermediate-size shape to execute a suborbital flight mission of a fair mid-complexity and suited for sounding rocket accommodation perspective;
- Many literature flight-cases were based on a diameter of 3 m (IRVE I, II, III and IV).

The next step in defining the configuration is to draw the re-entry vehicle body as well as the shape itself with respect to the complete body definition. Some main aspects were assumed:

- The system must have a cylindrical body: to optimize both folding and stowing of the IHS, but also to maximize accommodation of onboard equipment.
- The folding and stowing approach was previously experimented in EFESTO: umbrella-like folding is preferred because it will reduce the risk of “random and uncontrolled unfolding”, and it will allow for “regular/flowless” deployment and inflation. Indeed, the “fold-up” approach atop the nose of the vehicle is discarded because it appears to introduce a risk of entanglement and very difficult to be implemented.

- The folding length must be enough to allow an umbrella-like folding of the soft-part of the shield down-ward and around-ward.
- The back-shell (or trailing edge) cannot be sharp: it must be rounded because a sharp trailing edge cannot be properly manufactured with soft-fabrics material, and it would likely trigger high turbulence effects jeopardizing the aerodynamics of the shape itself.
- The cross-section of the shield can be either elliptical or circular.

Once given the drawing drivers mentioned above, the 3D CAD shape can be carried out. Two variants of the shape with elliptical and circular sections were designed as displayed in Figure 1. The circular configuration is the baseline (Figure 2) and is preferred due to an easiness to manufacture and a reduced volume to be inflated inducing a low amount of structural reinforcement.

Figure 1 – 2D CAD geometry sketch – elliptical and circular sections.

Figure 2 – View of the baseline configuration (circular shape)

3. AEROTHERMODYNAMIC INVESTIGATIONS

Based on these early aeroshape designs, aerothermodynamic investigations can be conducted. For the elliptical shape, a trajectory based on a 200 kg object has been investigated due to system constraints. For the circular shape, various trajectories have been studied considering various possible

vehicle weights: 200 kg, 250 kg, 300 kg, 350 kg. However, for the circular shape, CFD simulations have been carried out for flight points selected along 200 kg and 350 kg reference trajectories only.

For the calculation of aerodynamic coefficients, the reference surface is set to $S_{ref} = 7.07 \text{ m}^2$, while the reference length is set to $L_{ref} = 3 \text{ m}$. The moment coefficients are calculated at $[0; 0; 0]$ i.e. at the nose of the heat shield.

3.1. Meshes

2D-axisymmetric meshes have been built with ICEM solver for simulation at 0° of angle of attack while 3D meshes have been built with CENTAUR solver for cases where the angle of attack is not zero.

Figure 3 – 2D-axisymmetric structured mesh around the aeroshape - Mach 5.14 at 44.7 km – ICEM

Figure 4 - 3D unstructured mesh around the aeroshape - Mach 5.14 at 44.7 km – CENTAUR

The 2D-axisymmetric meshes are structured meshes composed of quad cells as illustrated in Figure 3 while the 3D unstructured meshes are composed of prismatic and tetra cells, as shown in Figure 4. For each flight conditions the exact position of the shock in front of the heat shield is captured in a very refined zone, composed of prismatic layers in the 3D mesh. To do so, the mesh is manually adapted from converged solutions obtained by numerical simulation. The

mesh adaptation process is repeated until the mesh cells are aligned with the shock and the shock is then captured in the dedicated fine zone. To properly capture the gradients at the wall, quad or prismatic layers have been prescribed near the wall: the size of the first cell being $1 \mu\text{m}$ with a stretching ratio of 1.1.

2D axisymmetric and 3D meshes are completely different: structured vs. unstructured mesh, quad cells vs. prismatic/tetra cells, constructed with ICEM vs. CENTAUR meshing solvers. To validate the mesh parameters used in 3D and further assess the influence of the mesh and the possible 3D effects on computed data, two simulations were performed at Mach 5.14 (max heat flux flight point along the 350 kg reference trajectory of the circular heat shield) at an angle of attack $\alpha = 0^\circ$ with meshes.

Figure 5 - Pressure and skin friction distributions around the IHS at Mach 5.14 and $\alpha = 0^\circ$. Blue line: 2D axisymmetric simulation. Red line: 3D simulation

Both meshes provide very similar flow topologies around the HIS. However, outside the refinement area, the 3D mesh becomes too coarse and the structures of the flow topology, as the recompression shock, are a bit dissipated. In hypersonic and supersonic regimes, except in the subsonic zones (as the recirculation areas and the front shock layer), quasi-zero information comes from downstream to upstream. So, a weaker resolution of the flow after the reattachment point has no tangible influence on the field upstream and thus on the wall quantities. So, as illustrated in Figure 5, wall pressure and the skin friction distributions obtained with the 2D-axisymmetric and the 3D meshes are quasi-identical. The

relative error between the axial force coefficient computed with the 2D-axisymmetric and 3D meshes is around 0.09%: $C_{A,2D-axi} = 1.3351$, $C_{A,3D} = 1.3339$ for Mach 5.14.

3.2. Numerical parameters

CFD computations have been conducted with the ONERA unstructured Navier-Stokes solver CHARME of the CEDRE platform. The Navier-Stokes equations are solved with a second-order finite-volume discretization in space, the flux vector splitting AUSM+ scheme associated to a Van Leer limiter. The time integration has been set to a one-step fully implicit approach. According to the trajectory flight conditions, atmospheric gas in the shock layer is assumed to be a perfect gas. The wall heat flux is calculated within two assumptions: radiative equilibrium at the wall with an emissivity $\epsilon = 0.8$ and by setting the wall temperature to 300 K (cold wall assumption).

According to both the Reynolds numbers of the considered flight points and non-rigid conical wall, the laminar-to-turbulent transition is assumed likely to occur at the wall. The boundary layer is thus supposed to be partially or fully turbulent. Thus, for the numerical simulations, a $k - \omega$ SST Menter model (two-equation model) is used with a vorticity source term P_k . This alternative option, calculating the production term using vorticity instead of deformation, is carried out to limit turbulence at the stagnation point or while crossing the shock.

In low-turbulence cases where it is difficult to guess any characteristic turbulent length scale as for external aerodynamics, the eddy viscosity ratio is especially convenient to use in order to obtain realistic inlet boundary conditions for the turbulence variables. The eddy viscosity ratio, $\frac{\mu_t}{\mu}$, is the ratio between the turbulent viscosity, μ_t , and the molecular dynamic viscosity, μ . The main advantage of using the eddy viscosity ratio is that it is a direct marker of how strong or weak is the turbulent viscosity compared to the molecular viscosity (laminar one) into the boundary layer. The eddy viscosity ratio is set between 1 and 10 for internal flows, while it should be between 0.2 and 1.3 for classical external flows as around airplane or cars. In our case, the atmospheric turbulence is quasi zero, corresponding to very low values of upstream eddy viscosity ratio.

Various values of the turbulence parameters have been considered (see Table 1) and their influences on the axial force coefficient and the wall convecto-diffusive heat flux have been studied at Mach 5.14, which is the peak heating flight point along the 350 kg reference trajectory of the circular aeroshape design.

As shown in Table 1, the turbulence parameters have no significant influence on the axial force coefficient for the Mach number under study. However, as illustrated in Figure 6, a visible influence is observed on the value of the convective-diffusive heat flux. Regarding the early phase

design, we will consider parameters set that could induce the most sizing heat flux values, i.e. $k = 1 J/kg$ and $\omega = 1000 s^{-1}$.

Table 1 - Influence of the turbulence parameter on the axial force coefficient

k (J/kg)	ω (s^{-1})	μ_t/μ	C_A Mach 5.14 at 44.7 km
1	1000	0.123	1.3351
10	10^5	0.012	1.3351
10	10^6	0.001	1.3352

Figure 6 - Influence of input turbulence parameters on the wall convective-diffusive heat flux distribution

3.3. Sensitivity analysis

3.3.1. Influence of the HIS shape

Two aeroshape designs have been considered during the early aeroshape design phase: elliptical shape and circular shapes, as illustrated in Figure 7. The aerodynamic coefficients as well as distributions of the wall pressure, skin friction and convective heat flux have been compared at two flights point selected on the 200 kg reference trajectories of the corresponding IHS without angle of attack: Peak Heating (PH) and Peak Pressure (PP) flight points. In other words, for example, the maximum PH flight point is not exactly the same for the two shapes:

- Elliptical shape: $H = 49.42$ km, $M = 5.07$, $V = 1672.73$
- Circular shape: $H = 49.63$ km, $M = 5.06$, $V = 1670.16$

These initial flow conditions variations induce small differences, almost no discernible, on the pressure, skin friction and wall heat flux around the nose and along the heat shield up to $y = 1.3$ m. Between $y = 1.3$ m and $y = 1.5$ m, the wall pressure, skin friction and wall heat flux variations are mainly due to variation of the shape shoulder of the HIS (Figure 8). Elliptical shape induces more important wall pressure, skin friction and wall heat flux around the trailing edge.

a) Elliptical shape b) Circular shape

Figure 7 - Elliptical and circular aeroshape designs

Figure 8 - Heat flux at the wall for two aeroshapes under study for two characteristic flight points along the 200 kg reference trajectories

The circular shape is largely preferred since it is a more efficient shape from a structural/mechanical point of view, it is easier to manufacture and it requires much less volume to inflate. In addition, circular IHS will imply less fabrics and less gas. Finally, the axial force coefficient (at Mach 5, $C_{A,elliptical\ shape} = 1.41$ and $C_{A,circular\ shape} = 1.34$) and heating level (Figure 8) are lower.

3.3.1. Influence of the flight conditions

To evaluate the influence of the trajectory on the aerodynamic axial coefficient and the wall heat flux, two flight points (PH and PP) have been selected along both the 200 kg and 350 kg reference trajectories for the circular aeroshape and at $\alpha = 0^\circ$. C_A levels are very similar (mean relative error between 0.1% and 0.3%), showing no significant influence of the flight point (altitude – Mach) during this hypersonic phase.

However, as expected, the conclusion is completely different when the convective heat flux is then considered (Figure 9). Indeed, the 350 kg reference trajectory is more critical than the 200 kg since the convective heat flux experienced by the IHS at Mach 5.1 (PH) is around +32% higher at the stagnation point and around +56% higher on the trailing edge. Although the values of the heat flux are less critical at Mach 3.7 (PP), the heat flux obtained for the flight point along the 350 kg reference trajectory is around +30% higher than the one

calculated at the equivalent flight point along the 200 kg reference trajectory.

Figure 9 - Comparison of the convective heat flux computed at maximum heat flux and pressure flight points along the 200 kg and 350 kg reference trajectories for the circular HIS

3.3.1. Influence of the wall temperature

The heat flux has been calculated assuming both the radiative equilibrium at the wall with an emissivity of 0.8 and by prescribing the wall temperature set to 300 K. Assuming radiative equilibrium at the wall leads to a maximization of the wall temperature, while assuming an isothermal wall leads to a maximization of the wall heat flux (Figure 10). In this early design phase, these two assumptions allow to take some necessary margins on the TPS and trajectory designs. The isothermal wall assumption being the most conservative, it is thus the one retained for the sizing of the heat shield.

Figure 10 - Influence of the wall temperature assumption on the wall heat flux for 3 flight points along the 350 kg reference trajectory for the circular HIS aeroshape.

3.3.1. Influence of the tube length

Since the actual rocket segment is shorter (call “tube size 2” or “V2” in the following figures) than the previous one considered (call “tube size 1” or “V1” in the following figures), the configurations of the tube and payload have been then modified (Figure 11). Due to system constraints, the size of the tube has been increased by 220 mm, while the total length of the aeroshape (from the nose to the back of the rocket segment) has been reduced by 216 mm. We aimed to determine the influence of this modification on the

aerodynamic coefficients and on the position of the pressure centre but also to ensure there is no significant influence on the back-shell wall heat flux.

Figure 11 - Modification of the rocket segment onto the circular aeroshape design

Figure 12 - Mach flow field around the circular HIS aeroshape for two tube lengths at Mach 5.14.

The sensitivity study has been conducted for two flight points along the 350 kg reference trajectory at $\alpha = 0^\circ$.

As illustrated in Figure 12, the modification of the tube and payload size has not a significant influence on the recirculation area. We still observe the presence of three bigger recirculation zones (1 main and two secondary ones). Moreover, the fluid reattachment point is still located far from the payload.

The pressure distribution is quasi-equivalent and it induces a very small variation of the axial force coefficient (between 0.06% and 0.45%) and the position of the pressure centre (between 0.2% and 0.7%). Moreover, the modification of the payload and tube size has no significant influence on the wall heat flux at the rear side of the IHS.

3.4. Building an aerothermodynamic database

Thus, a preliminary aerodynamic database has been built for the circular aeroshape design for two angles of attack values $[0^\circ; +5^\circ]$ and five Mach number $[1.4; 2; 3.7; 5.1; 6.8]$ values. This database provides the axial and normal force coefficients, the pitching moment coefficient, the drag and lift coefficients, the L/D ratio as well as the position of the center of pressure according to the Mach number and the angle of attack. This database outputs have been used for the flying quality analysis.

4. FLYING QUALITY ANALYSIS

The flying quality analysis [3], [4] provides outputs to system design, defining a feasible center of gravity domain in terms of the static stability of the vehicle, the aerodynamic efficiency in terms of L/D and angle of attack trimmability. For this purpose, the analysis is based on the inputs received from the 2D geometry and the aerodynamic database.

Relying on the aerodynamic database it is possible to outline important vehicle aerodynamic performance or flying qualities. For an arbitrary position of the center of gravity (CoG) the trim angle of attack (if any) is computed, and the associated L/D ratio is therefore obtained. For each CoG position, the static margin (SM) is also computed, as it provides an evaluation of the longitudinal stability of the vehicle. These three indicators define a criterion for outlining a viable CoG region as a function of the Mach number.

4.1. Assumptions

The analysis is performed for the circular shape geometry. The aerodynamic database provided contains static aerodynamic coefficients and the uncertainty level as a function of the angle of attack $[0^\circ; +5^\circ]$ and Mach number $[1.4; 2; 3.7; 5.1; 6.8]$. The current analysis only considers the longitudinal plane, with lateral force and moment coefficients (C_Y, C_n, C_l) set to zero.

The aerodynamic database is extended towards negative angles of attack to ease the understanding of the analysis. Aerodynamic coefficients are mirrored with respect the horizontal (XY) plane:

$$C_{A_{-5^\circ}} = C_{A_{5^\circ}}; C_{N_{-5^\circ}} = -C_{N_{5^\circ}}; C_{m_{-5^\circ}} = -C_{m_{5^\circ}}$$

The CoG variability studied covers a large part of the geometry, to scan an overshoot number of feasible positions (Figure 13):

- 60% of the L_{ref} along the longitudinal axis, from the nose of the vehicle.
- 20% of the L_{ref} along the lateral axis, centered over the X-axis.

Figure 13 - CoG variability analysed

The analysis results are referred to a flight mechanics reference frame (Figure 14), where:

- Origin is at the nose of the capsule.
- FM X-axis along the revolution axis, positive looking forward.
- FM Y-axis is normal to FM X-axis, positive pointing starboard (right-side of the vehicle when looking forward)
- FM Z-axis complete the right-hand system, positive pointing downwards.

Figure 14 - Flight-Mechanics reference frame

4.2. Nominal analysis

The offset of the CoG position with respect the longitudinal axis of the vehicle implies that the vehicle will naturally reach during the re-entry a trim angle of attack different from 0° . The range of possible CoG positions enable to trim the vehicle at angles of attack between -5° and 5° (Figure 15). To visualize a larger trimmable area, especially with higher lateral displacements, the angle of attack range of the aerodynamic database should be increased.

Figure 15 - Trim angle of attack variability at Mach number 2.06.

Static stability is assessed by the computation of the static margin (SM), normalized to the vehicle's reference length. Displacing the CoG towards the nose of the vehicle provides higher static margins, allowing also a higher variation over the lateral CoG Z-position of the vehicle. Figure 16 shows the static margin variability with respect the Mach number only for CoG positions on the longitudinal axis of the capsule. For a fixed CoG, the SM increases as the capsule slow down.

Figure 16 - Static margin variability wrt Mach number

4.3. Variability analysis

Uncertainties provided with the aerodynamic database imply a variability that can be assessed on the static margin. Maximum and minimum values are shown as a band around the nominal values (thick solid lines), depicting a preliminary assessment of the static margin variability.

The analysis is performed using 1σ uncertainties, which are applied by addition to the static coefficients: $\Delta CA = CA \pm UCA$, $\Delta CN = CN \pm UCN$, $\Delta Cm = Cm \pm UCm$. The results show that the maximum variability is at Mach numbers 2 to 4, where it represents around 7% of the SM delta. It decreases towards higher Mach numbers. Minimum variability is found at Mach number 6.8, where it represents less than 1% of the SM delta.

5. CONCLUSION

CFD simulations have been performed around two aeroshape designs at various flight conditions along different possible trajectories, with and without an angle of attack. The analysis of the flow topology, aerodynamic force and moment coefficients and wall heating distributions brought arguments to make an optimized choice between the HIS aeroshape designs and associated trajectories under study. 350kg trajectory was chosen wrt to mission objectives and it was confirmed no effect induced by the backshell length modification regarding aerodynamic and heating parameters levels. Aerodynamic and aerothermodynamic databases have been used as inputs by other partners to consolidate reference trajectory, flying quality, TPS and HMS sensors choices.

Through flying qualities analysis, a preliminary assessment of different CoG locations was carried out for the current capsule's geometry. A feasible area for the CoG has been identified where a trim angle of attack exists, with a positive static margin, assuring the static stability of the capsule during the complete duration of the entry.

The feasible CoG area is limited to angles of attack between -5° and 5° . When flying with an AoA of 5° the L/D efficiency reaches maximum values of 0.06 for the further lateral positions of the CoG. In case the design point from mission design requires higher L/D values, it will require to explore higher than 5° flight angles of attack.

Based on heritage, it is established that a reasonable objective for the static stability should be a $SM \geq 15\%$.

Based on the current mass distribution assessment, the calculated CoG location on the CAD model is at 1149 mm from the nose of the capsule. According to the map shown above, for this point the vehicle exhibits static margin values always positive for the complete entry phase.

In the promising CoG position nominal analysis shows that the worst static margin is found at the beginning of the entry, with a 14.49% of SM at Mach number 6.8, hence a bit lower than 15% but still very close to. Further down the descent, SM increases to 26% at Mach number 1.41.

The variability analysis points out that at Mach numbers 2 to 4 the SM can decrease (total band at this Mach number is 7.31% wide), but between these Mach numbers the SM nominal value is positive enough to compensate the negative-side of the band, with nominal values around 20% to 24%. The minimum variability found at high Mach numbers is explained by the lower nominal values of the pitch moment coefficient, which present minimum values at this Mach number.

As a matter of the fact, the SRR configuration featuring a CoG location of 1149 mm from the nose, exhibits static margin values from $\sim 14\%$ to $\sim 26\%$ during the complete entry of the capsule and this is a very satisfactory result.

Subsequently, the following actions will be carried out within the framework of this project:

- Extend the aerothermodynamic database (AE-ATDB) to higher values of angle of attack; extend the AE-ATDB in rarefied regime
- Execute dynamic derivatives assessment and related FQA to verify the dynamic stability of the system during re-entry and ensure that the system maintain the proper attitude in the experimental part of the atmospheric flight.
- Execute coupled simulations CFD-FEM to evaluation the wall deformation and its effect on the aerothermodynamic quantities.

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More information at:

- <https://www.he-icarus-project.eu/>
- <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134997>

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